

**THE EXPRESSION OF A SOCIAL NATIONAL WORD WITHIN
THE ENGLISH INTERPRETATION OF THE WORK OF TAHIR MALIK "DEVILDOM"**

Zarifa Gafurovna Ruzimurodova

Lecturer of the Department of Foreign Languages of Pedagogical institute of Bukhara State
University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509629>

ABSTRACT. This article composes almost interpretation issue of social national words in interpretation of Tohir Malik's "Devildom". Analysis of national words in interpretation is defined here.

Key words: national words, national color, translation, transliteration, word by word translation, literary translation, analogue translation

Introduction. From science it is evident that interpretation could be an exceptionally fragile handle that requires persistent, profitable investigate from the interpreter in arrange to apply their skills and reproduce them. Its pertinence lies within the reality that a work new to the peruse will fundamentally reach through a interpreter, and an elective to the reproduced work to the first is exceptionally critical in getting otherworldly food from this work or in getting a common vision. At the same place, A.Muminova says this: "a person engaged in translation, that is, a translator, is a bridge between two languages, two peoples, through his ability to translate, the finest facets of the people, the nation are reflected" [Muminova, 2016]. After all, the culture, way of life, traditions and worldview of an entire nation are necessarily manifested in its language. Therefore, the responsibility that the translator bears in this regard is very great. Especially noteworthy is the translator's approach to translating national words related to a particular folk language, that is, to specific words. Therefore, a translator who has managed to translate correctly using the most accessible methods, while preserving the national flavor, can be unconditionally called a master

of his craft. For example, words and concepts found in the Uzbek language may be absent in other languages or differ in content, form, volume. But, considering that it is the means of expressing our national identity that are one of them, the translation problems associated with the transfer of specific aspects of our culture to the reader are facing all of us crosswise.

Main part. From the works of scientists who worked on the theory of translation, such as G'.Salomov, Q.Musayev, we know that in translation there is a role of specific words (traditional words). Traditional cultural words-these are words in which each state depends on its culture, expressing its own Traditional color. Specific words can be divided into the following types, depending on their characteristics:

1. Words related to religions and religious rites: mullah, hojiaka, hojiona, bishop, archbishop, pope, etc.;
2. Words denoting folk customs: kurpacha (matrass), challari (party), beshik (cradle), muchal party(the day when the men celebrate every 13 years), circumcision wedding, etc.;
3. Words about traditional coloring: doppi(duppi)(the thing for putting on head in Central Asia), chopon(cloth as a coat which is used in Central Asia), hat, kepka are such words.

Discussion. In the translation of specific words, we can use the following methods blessed. From such methods of E.Ochilov we know 3 of them, F.Bakiyev highlighted the achievements and shortcomings of each method on the example of 5 of them. These are: 1) transliteration or transcribing, 2) subheading comments and explanation, 3) word by word translation, 4) analogy (translation with similar words), 5)pictorial translations.

1. Transliteration-this method is to adapt to other letters in the translation language by changing the letters of the word in the original. "The main reason why Traditional specific words are given in translation by transliteration is that the Traditional specific language tools used in the original are not available in the translation language"⁹, 2013, 32].

Ичкари кириб, меҳмонхона эшигини қия очди. Ўртадаги устол устига дастурхон ёзилмаган, китоб-қоғозлар бетартиб сочилиб ётибди. ("Шайтанат" Тоҳир Малик, 143 бет)

*Coming inside he opened the door of sitting room half. There wasn't **dastarkhan** on the table in the middle of the room, papers were untidily. ("Devildom" Tohir Malik, p.218).*

Sometimes such a translation does not even affect the overall plot, or meaning of the work.

2. Often, words that have moved into translation by the method of transliteration or transcription are used under the heading comments and understandings in order to familiarize the reader with the meaning or concept that they mean. The following words are also translated in this way. But In the translations of T.Malik's "Devildom" translated by I.M.Tokhtasinov and N.M.Kambarov, in most cases, this method was not used, and this, as noted above, gives the reader a lot of difficulty and does not allow to fully understand the work:

*Аҳадбей отаси кирганида **хонтахта** остига яширган шишани олиб, **пиёлаларга** ароқ куйди-да, «Соғ бўл», деб кўтарди. ("Шайтанат" Тоҳир Малик, 161 бет)*

*When father entered Ahmadbey took out the vodka from under the **khantahta** and filled the **piala** and drank saying "Be health". ("Devildom" Tohir Malik, p.244)*

Inside the work, many such words were used, but what is meant by such words as this to the English reader, who is a yacht, is not given as an explanation. For the first time in the game, when similar specific words are used, either by opening a bracket before the same word, or at the bottom of the same page, the same word should be commented. Below we give an example of this:

*"He ate two pieces of **handalak** (a small honey melon) and drank several **pialas** (a drinking bowl (as used in Central Asia)) of tea" ["Starry nights Babur" P.Qodirov, 2019, 10]*

"Faqat bir-ikki tilim handalak yediyu uch-to'rt piyola choy ichdi" ["Yulduzli tunlar" P.Qodirov, 2018, 10]

3. Sometimes there will be an opportunity to save, even if the words in the original are not an alternative in the translation language. This can be achieved by calcification. Word by word translation this is a literal word translation. It can also be seen in the sentence below that this method is used:

*Бу йигитнинг **мушдек юрагини қоядек дард** босиб турганини Зелихоннинг синчков нигоҳи илғади. Зелихон дардини яшира оладиган одамни яхши кўрарди. Ҳасратини ҳар кимга тўкиб солувчи эркакдан дўст чиқмайди, деб ишонарди. ("Шайтанат" Тоҳир Малик, 49 бет)*

*Zelihon felt that boy's **small heart**. Zelihon liked a man who could hide his sorrow. He believed that he couldn't make a friend with men who told his suffer and torments everyone. ("Devildom" Tohir Malik, p.81)*

As can be seen from this passage, when looking at the originality of the work, two expressions were used in the Uzbek language: "**mushtdek yurak**" and "**qoyadek dard**". But the English translator described the first phrase as "small heart". Here the translator uses the word by word translation method. This in turn can make it difficult for the reader to understand the work exactly as the author wrote it. Since this is exactly the English language in translation, the fact that translators are not representatives of that state, this culture, the translation of Uzbek translators is certainly not translated in the spirit of that state, in accordance with their culture. If we touch on the second phrase the phrase "**qoyadek dard**", then this phrase is not reflected in the translation at all.

4. Analogy is the transfer of the word in the original language into the translation language with a similar and alternative understanding. "In the translation language, when sometimes it meets the meanings of linguistic means in the original to a certain extent closer to the meaning of meaningful unity, they differ from their conditional alternatives in terms of characteristic, form, size-quantity, this discrepancy does not allow mutual exchange in translation" [2, 2005, 93]. As an example, we can see the following passage from the 1st book of the novel "Devildom" by Tahir Malik:

*-Асадбек «керак эмас», деган маънода қўл қўтарди. Манзура бу ишорани кўрмагандай нариги уйга кириб **кўрпача** қўтариб чиқди. ("Шайтанат" Тоҳир Малик, 67 бет)*

*-Asadbek waved his hand as he said "do not need". But Manzura brought **mattress** as if she didn't see his gesture. ("Devildom" Tohir Malik, p.109)*

As can be seen from the passage above, the reason why the translator could not find the exact equivalent of the word mattress, which the author gave in the original, the word mattress, known to the English as an alternative, used, and this did not exactly affect the general contextual meaning of the work.

5. Literary translation-to give the meaning of these expressions with the help of variable word combinations [10]. There are such cases, when in the translation language there is no equivalent and similar phraseological combination to the original, it is translated in an illustrative way. Even in the translation of Traditional words, the words are transferred to the translator, as described by a certain designation. The following words are also translated like this:

*Ҳеч замонда **даҳлиз** ҳам испалний бўларканми, — деди аммаси унинг норозилигини писанд қилмай. (“Шайтанат” Тоҳир Малик,127 бет)*

*- How an **ante-room** may be a bedroom?-said his aunt omitting his complaint. (“Devildom” Tohir Malik, p.192)*

*Ҳаммаёқни **хотинчалиш** босиб кетган. (“Шайтанат” Тоҳир Малик,80 бет)*

*All men **look like women**. (“Devildom” Tohir Malik, p.127)*

In these excerpts, the word “hallway” is expressed by the word “ante-room”, and the word “wife” is reflected by the phrase "look like woman".

These methods were used productively in the preservation of the color of “Devildom” by T.Malik, but when the method of transliteration was used, its interpretation was not given at all. Such words should at least be explained what they mean. This will help the reader to understand the work in full.

This article describes the image of imaginary diseases in the stories of Edgar Allan Poe and the reasons for writing about diseases. The allegory and symbolism by depicting the Red Death.¹

The article is devoted to the analysis of the The Magic Hat book, written by popular Uzbek writer Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboyev, from the position of classification elements introduced by famous Russian philosopher, literary critic and scholar Mikhail Mikhailovich Bakhtin.²

¹ Akhmedovna, B. M., & Shakhnoza, B. (2022). The Image of Disease in Edgar Allan Poe’s “The Masque of the Red Death”. *Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT*, 2(1), 19-22.

² Kadirova, N. A. (2020). ANALYSIS OF TRANSFORMATION MOTIFS IN THE MAGIC HAT BOOK BY KHUDOYBERDI TUKHTABOYEV, THROUGH THE PRISM OF MIKHAIL BAKHTIN’S THEORIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 405-408.

The depiction of natural landscapes given in works of art is one of the factors that demonstrate the creative artistic skill.³

В современной методике так же, как и много лет назад, актуальной и нерешенной до сих пор остается проблема поиска и выбора наиболее эффективных и рациональных методов преподавания иностранных языков, соответствующих современным условиям обучения и отвечающих требованиям стандартов современного образования.⁴

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory.⁵

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.⁶

This lesson plan format moves from teachers to centered student. In order to keep this standard lesson plan format from becoming monotonous, it is seminal to memorize that there are a number of variations that can be applied within the various segments of the lesson plan format.⁷

This article deals with the analysis of pastiche in literature, particularly in "The Lightning Thief" by American author Rick Riordan. The research identifies pastiche as a term, which is applied to a literary work that is a broad mixture of things-such as themes, concepts, and characters-imitated from different literary works.⁸

³ Kabilova, F., & Tokhirova, T. K. English Translation of Abdullah Qadiri's Novel "Days Gone by" and Its Reflection Skills. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(10), 304-306.

⁴ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

⁵ Gafurova, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

⁶ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

⁷ Nodirova, N. N., & Temirova, P. M. (2022). Principles of designing lesson plans for teaching ESL or EFL. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 5, 10-12.

⁸ Khabibullaeva, R. M. (2020). ANALYSIS OF PASTICHE IN THE NOVEL "THE LIGHTNING THIEF" BY RICK RIORDAN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 958-961.

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham's short story "The Book Bag". It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.⁹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day.¹⁰

В этой статье дается краткий обзор антропонимов, их функций статуса, который они получают от этих, и их специфики.¹¹

The article is about the development of the Soviet era of Uzbek educational dictionary. The educational dictionaries created during this period served mainly to teach Russian in national schools.¹²

This article deals with the description of synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language published in different periods, the systematic description of the similarities and differences between the explanations of synonyms in the publications.¹³

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the right of citizens to vote and to be elected, the foundations of the national electoral system, the basis of which are the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and ratification by Uzbekistan, constituting the principles of democracy, including independence,

⁹ Куницька, І. (2014). Роман-біографія як жанровий різновид модерністського роману (С. Моем Місяць і мідяки"). *Сучасні літературознавчі студії*, (11), 342-348.

¹⁰ NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

¹¹ Орипова, К. (2022). ОНОМАСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОСТИ ВО ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 8(8). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4712

¹² Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). HISTORY OF CREATING FIRST BILINGUAL AND REGULATORY EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(1), 147-181.

¹³ Rustamovna, M. G. (2020). Presenting synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 6, 117-120.

legitimacy, transparency and fairness, enshrined and recognized in other international legal instruments.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

Conclusion. In conclusion, in the process of translating Traditional words, the translator is required to translate them, taking into account the achievements and shortcomings of these methods, having preserved the Traditional coloration. E.It is also not surprising that Ochilov in his book "issues of artistic translation" called the part dedicated to the preservation of the Traditional color in the translation of the work "problems of problems", of course. Therefore, when choosing a method of translation, it is especially important to translate the text due to both stylistic and genre characteristics.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Akhmedovna, B. M., & Shakhnoza, B. (2022). The Image of Disease in Edgar Allan Poe's "The Masque of the Red Death". *Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT*, 2(1), 19-22.
2. Kadirova, N. A. (2020). ANALYSIS OF TRANSFORMATION MOTIFS IN THE MAGIC HAT BOOK BY KHUDOYBERDI TUKHTABOYEV, THROUGH THE PRISM OF MIKHAIL BAKHTINS THEORIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 405-408.
3. Kabilova, F., & Tokhirovna, T. K. English Translation of Abdullah Qadiri's Novel "Days Gone by" and Its Reflection Skills. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(10), 304-306.
4. Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.
5. Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹⁴ Tolibjonovich, M. T., & Toxirjonovich, S. D. (2021). The Institutional Mechanisms Of The Development Of The Electoral System In Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(8), 4378-4384.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

6. Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.
7. Nodirovna, N. N., & Temirovna, P. M. (2022). Principles of designing lesson plans for teaching ESL or EFL. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 5, 10-12.
8. Khabibullaeva, R. M. (2020). ANALYSIS OF PASTICHE IN THE NOVEL "THE LIGHTNING THIEF" BY RICK RIORDAN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 958-961.
9. Куницька, І. (2014). Роман-біографія як жанровий різновид модерністського роману (С. Моем Місяць і мідяки"). *Сучасні літературознавчі студії*, (11), 342-348.
10. NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).
11. Орипова, К. (2022). ОНОМАСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОСТИ ВО ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 8(8).
извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4712
12. Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). HISTORY OF CREATING FIRST BILINGUAL AND REGULATORY EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(1), 147-181.
13. Rustamovna, M. G. (2020). Presenting synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 6, 117-120.
14. Tolibjonovich, M. T., & Toxirjonovich, S. D. (2021). The Institutional Mechanisms Of The Development Of The Electoral System In Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(8), 4378-4384.
15. Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.